

The Effect of Organizational Competence and Commitment to Career Management in Improving Employee Performance (Case Study at PT Nuvision Internasional Indonesia)

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Abstract:- This study aims to determine the effect of competence and organizational commitment on career management in improving employee performance (a case study at PT Nuvision Internasional Indonesia). The research method used is the quantitative method. The population and sample used in this study were 80 people. Analysis and testing techniques use the Partial Least Square Structural Equation Model with the help of the SmartPLS application. The test results show that Competence has a positive and significant effect on employee performance with the largest dimension is attitudes. Meanwhile, organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on employee performance, with the largest dimension of organizational commitment was normative organizational commitment. Career management variables is partially mediating of competence to performance while its mediates fully for organizational commitment to employee performance. With the largest dimension of career management which affecting employee performance was the dimension of availability of supporting data of career management.

Keywords:- Competency, Organizational Commitment, Career Management, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of technology certainly brings changes in life that cannot be avoided. The human factor is used as one of the elements of its implementation that must be able to follow all these changes.

The activity most often assessed by a company is employee performance, that is, how the employee can do everything relating to a job, position, or role within the company.

Nuvision Internasional Indonesia is a management consulting firm specializing in business and technology transformation such as strategy and operations management, digital transformation, enterprise architecture, business process management, SOA, IT strategy planning, global risk and compliance, and IT security consulting services. Based on data from the personnel department of PT. Nuvision Internasional Indonesia is known that the level of absenteeism in the last three years, reached 2-4% per month. According to the leadership of PT. Nuvision Internasional Indonesia, absenteeism rate of more than 3% needs to be

avoided because it can reduce employee performance.

One indicator of increasing the level of employee absenteeism, where the condition of the level of employee absenteeism at PT. Nuvision Internasional Indonesia in 2020 was 3.09%, in 2021 it increased to 3.12% and in 2022 it increased again to 3.15%, where the tolerated absenteeism rate was below 3%. Performance report data can be seen to have decreased, as for the personnel business commitment (PBC) of PT. Nuvision Internasional Indonesia for the period 2018-2022 where in 2020 it was 60.86%, an increase in 2021 of 69.01%, an increase in 2022 of 74.55%.

The biggest factor affecting employee performance variables is the decline in PT. Nuvision Internasional Indonesia is an organizational commitment variable obtained by 30% and a competency variable obtained by 27%, while career management variables are obtained by 17% from 30 respondents. Results of the Organizational Commitment Pre-Survey involving 30 respondents.

The training I received certainly provided benefits for career development by obtaining a score of 40% approval and 60% disapproval. From the display of the company's career management pre-survey results, PT Nuvision Internasional Indonesia strives to increase the productivity of its employees. Career management is the first step towards the career path of an employee, employees are required to participate in work as needed.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES

A. Human Resource Management

According to Hasibuan (2017), that human resource management is . The field of management specifically studies the relationship and role of human management in corporate organizations.

B. Career Management

According to Yahya et al. (2004) career is not something that must be handed over to every employee, but the career must be managed by the organization to ensure efficient allocation of human resources and capital.

According to Adam Smale (2018), the dimensions of career management include:

➤ *Existence of career plans and career procedures in HR management*

Plan about the possibility of an employee of an organization or company as an individual in the process of promotion or position according to his requirements and abilities.

➤ *Availability of Career Opportunities*

Opportunity to be able to improve and improve the effectiveness of work implementation by workers in order to be more able to provide the best contribution in realizing company goals.

➤ *Career Support*

Understand how employees' careers, behaviors, and decisions, such as finding and accepting jobs, deciding to keep working with the organization, drawing up career plans, seeking new job experiences, and striving to achieve career goals (career insights).

➤ *Supporting Data for Career*

Supporting data used to complement key data that can support success. Supporting data is obtained through documentation. The function of supporting data as complementary data to the main data is not analyzed as well as the main data.

C. Employee Performance

Employee performance is a result achieved by workers in their work according to certain criteria that apply to a particular job, Robbins (2006). Lin, (2013) stated that performance is a work achievement that can be shown by an employee or employee as a result of work that can be achieved during a certain period of time in doing the work charged to him, based on skills, experience and sincerity. According to Nurma Asri Asharini (2018), performance dimensions include:

➤ *Quantity*

A unit of measure associated with the amount of work and expressed in numerical measures. This can be seen from the results of employee work at work and the use of certain time and speed of time in completing their duties and responsibilities.

➤ *Quality*

A result that can be measured from the level of efficiency and effectiveness of an employee in doing a job. In other words, these employees are able to carry out work according to the standards given by the company effectively and efficiently, then supported by other resources in achieving company goals.

➤ *Implementation of Duties*

Employees are able to perform their work accurately or with no mistakes. Then an employee is not relied on in carrying out duties according to instructions at work and how an employee can take the initiative and work carefully to complete the job well.

➤ *Responsibility*

Human awareness of intentional or unintentional behavior or actions. Responsibility as a manifestation of awareness regarding the obligation of employees to carry out the work given by the company.

D. Competence

Palan (2007), states that competence has various definitions, but the definition that is worthy of acceptance is that competence is defined as the basic characteristics of a person who have a causal relationship with the reference criteria of effectiveness or excellence in a particular job or situation. Competency Dimension.

According to Daria Podmetina (2018), the dimensions of competence include:

➤ *Skills*

In order to improve the performance of an employee, one of the supporting factors is the skill level of the employee itself. Competency is an ability to do a job based on skills and knowledge and supported by the work attitude required of the job.

➤ *Knowledge*

Symptoms that are encountered and acquired by man through reason are then combined with understanding and the potential to know only to be capable and to be informed.

➤ *Social Role*

The behavior expected of individuals is in accordance with their social status, so that the role can also function to regulate one's behavior.

➤ *Self-Image*

The whole of the views in various roles and as views of perceived personality traits such as loyal, honest, friendly.

➤ *Attitude*

The response of a person who is still closed to the presence of a stimulus or object expresses that attitude as readiness or willingness to act and not from the implementation of a particular motive.

E. Organizational Commitment

Organizational commitment according to Robbins (2007) is "the degree to which an employee takes sides with a particular organization and its goals, and intends to maintain membership in that organization." Based on this description, organizational commitment is the relationship between employees and the organization which is indicated by the desire to maintain organizational membership, accept organizational values and goals and be willing to strive for the achievement of organizational goals and continuity. According to Darwish Abdulrahman Yousef (2016), the dimensions of organizational commitment include:

➤ *Affective Commitment*

Focuses on an employee's emotional attachment identified with involvement in the organization. It is characterized by the comfort of the organization and the desire of employees to stay. Employees with strong affective commitment stay in an organization because they want to do so.

➤ *Sustainable Organization Commitment*

This commitment focuses on the employee's desire to stay in the organization because of the calculation of profit and loss where the perceived economic value of staying in an organization is compared to leaving the organization.

➤ *Normative Organizational Commitment*

This commitment focuses on the feelings of employees who are required to remain in their organization because of pressure from others. Employees who have a high level of normative commitment will certainly pay attention to what others say about leaving the organization. Then don't want to disappoint your boss and worry if coworkers think badly of the resignation.

F. Framework of Thought and Hypothesis Development

Fig. 1: Frame of Mind

➤ *Research Hypothesis:*

- H1 : Competency has a significant positive effect on career management.
- H2 : Competency has a significant positive effect on employee performance.
- H3 : Organizational commitment has a significant positive effect on career management.
- H4 : Organizational commitment has a significant positive effect on employee performance.
- H5 : Career management has a positive effect on employee performance.
- H6 : Competency positively affects employee performance through career management.
- H7 : Organizational commitment positively affects employee performance through career management.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The type of research design used in this study is quantitative descriptive research with a causal research approach (method). According to Sugiyono (2018) quantitative data is a research method based on positivistic (concrete data), research data in the form of numbers to be measured using statistics as a calculation test tool, related to the problem under study to produce a conclusion. The types and sources of data used in this study are Primary Data and Secondary Data. The data collection method used for this research is the Literature Study and Instrument Quality Test

Questionnaire in the study, namely Validity Test and Reality Test. The population in this study is all employees of PT Nuvision International Indonesia as many as 80 people. . The sampling technique in this study uses a census, by taking all members of the population as respondents. In this study the sample used amounted to 80 people *non-probability sampling* with saturated samples. For this reason, the sample used is more than the minimum requirements required in this model.

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

It is known that the majority of the last education they have, namely Bachelor as many as 70 people or 88%, there are respondents with a working period of <1 year as many as 8 people or 10%, respondents with a working period of 1-10 years as many as 53 people or 66%, respondents with a working period of 10-15 years as many as 14 people or 18%, and respondents with a working period of more than 15 years as many as 5 people or 6%.

A. *Instrument Quality Test Results*

By using the significance level of 5% as a test standard, it can be seen that all measuring indicators of all variables have a product moment correlation coefficient value that results in a significance level (calculation result) of less than 5% each. While the calculation results for the test have a Cronbach's Alpha value greater than 0.6.

B. Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Fig. 2: Path Coefficient Measurement PLS Algorithm

C. Convergent Validity Test Results

In addition to outer loading values, convergent validity can be assessed based on Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values. The AVE value of each variable in the measurement model used in this study has a value of >0.5 with AVE values

of 0.680 for employee performance variables, 0.728 for commitment variables, 0.637 for competency variables, and 0.617 for career management variables. So it can be stated that this measurement model is valid and can be used for further testing.

D. Reliability Test Results

Table 1: Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Reliability
Employee Performance	0.957	0.962	Reliable
Commitment	0.953	0.960	Reliable
Competence	0.959	0.963	Reliable
Career Management	0.943	0.951	Reliable

All variables used in the measurement model are reliable because they have Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values of >0.7. So it can be stated that the measurement model used is reliable and can be used for further testing.

is included in the range of 0.50-0.75 which means it has a substantial or strong influence. The Q2 value for the model in this study was 0.444 for employee performance and 0.316 for career management. So it can be stated that the model used has predictive-relevance because it has a value of Q2>0.

E. Results of R2 Value and Q2 Value

The R2 value for each dependent variable is for career management. Where the R2 value of the dependent variable

F. SRMR value

The SRMR value is 0.079, where the SRMR value has met the cut-off value of <0.10. So it can be stated that the model used is good.

G. Test the hypothesis

Table 2: Hypothesis Test Results

Influence	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics ((O/STDEV))	P Values	Information
Competence -> Career Management	0.277	0.272	0.112	2.468	0.014	Influential positive and Significant
Competence -> Employee Performance	0.468	0.458	0.111	4.233	0,000	Influential positive and Significant
-> Commitment to Career Management	0.495	0.496	0.104	4.754	0,000	Influential positive and Significant
-> Commitment to Employee Performance	0.080	0.081	0.119	0.666	0,506	Influential positive and not Significant
Career Management -> Employee Performance	0.361	0.363	0.083	4.333	0,000	Influential positive and Significant

V. DISCUSSION

A. Hypothesis 1

Hypothesis 1 is accepted and stated that there is a positive and significant influence of competence on career management. This is in accordance with research conducted by Pangaribu and Sihombing (2021) which states that there is a positive influence between competence and employee performance. Where the most influential dimension is attitude on the variable competence. A positive attitude is needed to support success in the work environment.

Researchers conducted interviews with 5 employees to find out their opinions on the hypothesis and also for other hypotheses. Based on interviews conducted, it is known that employees feel that with a good attitude, such as obeying rules, diligent and disciplined about their time, it will be easier to manage their careers through career management. This opinion is in accordance with Hypothesis 1 which states that there is a positive and significant influence of competence on career management.

B. Hypothesis 2

Hypothesis 2 is accepted and stated that there is a positive and significant influence of competence on employee performance. This is in accordance with research conducted by Distyawaty (2017) which states that competence and career development have a significant positive effect on performance. Where the most influential dimension is attitude on the variable competence. A positive attitude is necessary to improve performance.

Based on interviews conducted with 5 employees, it is known that they feel that there is a good attitude, such as obeying the rules, diligent and disciplined about their time in the work done. Then the employee will be able to more easily complete his work. Of course, these competencies must be relevant to the work done. So that the attitude of obeying the rules, diligent and disciplined about their time can encourage the achievement of maximum employee performance. This

opinion is in accordance with Hypothesis 2 which states that there is a positive and significant influence of competence on employee performance.

C. Hypothesis 3

Hypothesis 3 is accepted and stated that there is a positive and significant influence of commitment to career management. This is in accordance with research conducted by Mardikaningsih (2021) which states that the results are a positive relationship between career management and organizational commitment. Where the most influential dimension is normative organizational commitment on organizational commitment variables. Positive relationships and relationships are needed to improve performance.

Based on interviews conducted with 5 employees, it is known that a good relationship is a factor that shows the organization's trust in employees in doing work. They feel that the trust support provided by the organization can make it easier for employees to develop their careers. The organization's commitment to employee career development is carried out through a good career management process in the company. In addition, the existence of a good organizational relationship creates a sense of animation of obligations and ownership of the work done. This opinion is in accordance with Hypothesis 3 which states that there is a positive and significant influence of commitment to career management.

D. Hypothesis 4

Hypothesis 4 was rejected and stated that there was no significant effect of organizational commitment on employee performance. This is in accordance with research conducted by Ginanjar (2017) stating that organizational commitment does not have a significant effect on employee performance. Organizational commitment cannot have a significant effect on employee performance without commitment by the employees themselves.

Based on interviews conducted with 5 employees, it is known that organizational commitment can motivate employees in doing their jobs. But this cannot be done optimally without the comfort that the company should be able to provide to employees. Sometimes employees feel uncomfortable with the contract they have. So that employees only do work limited to the target or task given without striving for innovation that should be done. This causes no improvement to the performance produced by employees. This opinion is in accordance with Hypothesis 4 which states that there is no positive and significant influence of commitment to employee performance.

E. Hypothesis 5

Hypothesis 5 is accepted and stated that there is a positive and significant influence of career management on employee performance. This is in accordance with research conducted by Tiana (2021) which states that career management for employees is a form of business in employee career development that fosters commitment from employees to build their careers within the company. Where the most influential is the existence of supporting data in career management variables. Someone who likes experience and expertise will then drive his career.

Based on interviews conducted with 5 employees, it is known that employees believe that a good career management process can improve the performance produced by employees. They feel that career management can manage and optimize all the potential possessed by employees in doing work such as by placing in accordance with experience or helping by improving other skills such as appropriate certifications in supporting their work. Career management can provide appropriate positions and jobs for employees so that they can produce maximum performance. In addition, good career management can encourage employees to innovate in their work. This opinion is in accordance with Hypothesis 5 which states that there is a positive and significant influence of career management on employee performance.

F. Hypothesis 6

Hypothesis 6 is accepted and it is stated that competence has a positive and significant influence on employee performance through career management as a mediating variable. This is in accordance with research conducted by Solikhin (2018) which states that there is a significant influence of competence and career management on employee performance. Career management can manage and develop competencies possessed by employees to be able to improve the performance produced by employees.

Based on interviews conducted with 5 employees, it is known that career management can mediate competence in employee performance. Employees feel that career management can manage and develop the competencies possessed by employees. In addition, with career management, employees can also get positions or jobs that are in accordance with their competencies. So that employees can further optimize themselves with support in doing work. Where it can improve and maximize the performance produced by employees. This opinion is in accordance with

Hypothesis 6 which states that there is a positive and significant influence of competence on employee performance through performance management as a partial mediating variable.

G. Hypothesis 7

Hypothesis 7 is accepted and stated that commitment has a positive and significant influence on employee performance through career management as a mediating variable. This is in accordance with research conducted by Putra (2022) which states that the results of research show that career management has a real influence on the formation of organizational commitment. Career management demonstrates an organization's commitment to the empowerment and development of employees in its career. Where with this can improve the performance produced by employees.

Based on interviews conducted with 5 employees, it is known that career management can mediate commitment to full employee performance. As explained earlier that organizational commitment cannot have a significant direct influence on performance, but employees will be able to more easily and maximally perform if the organization's commitment is mediated by good career management. A good career management process can bridge an employee's organizational commitment to the organization. Employees will feel more comfortable in doing work and career development because of the support in career. So that employees will not feel too burdened with the work contract they have. It can also encourage employees to create innovation in their work. Where it can optimize and improve the performance produced by employees. This opinion is in accordance with Hypothesis 7 which states that there is a positive and significant influence of commitment to employee performance through career management as a full mediating variable.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

A. Conclusion

Based on the results of research and discussion in the previous chapters, several conclusions can be stated as follows:

Competency has a positive and significant effect on the career management of PT Nuvison International Indonesia. The attitude dimension has the highest value compared to other dimensions in the competency variable. Thus it can be concluded that, a good attitude such as completing tasks appropriately and quickly, discipline towards time, and obeying the rules, career management will also increase.

Competency has a positive and significant effect on the performance of PT Nuvison International Indonesia employees. The attitude dimension has the highest value compared to other dimensions in the competency variable. Thus it can be concluded that, a good attitude, such as completing tasks appropriately and quickly, discipline with time, and obeying the rules, employee performance will increase.

Organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on the career management of PT Nuvision International Indonesia. The normative organizational commitment dimension has the highest value compared to other dimensions in the organizational commitment variable. Thus it can be concluded that relations between colleagues, hesitation and loyalty to the company can improve the career management of an employee.

Organizational commitment has a positive but not significant effect on the performance of PT Nuvision International Indonesia employees. The normative organizational commitment dimension has the highest value compared to other dimensions in the organizational commitment variable. So it can be concluded that the relationship between colleagues, hesitation and loyalty to the company can affect in terms of improving employee performance but not significantly, so that the high organizational commitment of an employee, does not necessarily improve the performance of the employee.

Career management has a positive and significant effect on the performance of PT Nuvision International Indonesia employees. The supporting data dimension for career has the highest value compared to other dimensions in career management variables. It can be concluded that employees who have other skills to support careers are influential in terms of improving employee performance, which means the more other skills to support careers, the higher the performance of these employees.

Career management as a mediator of the relationship between employee competence and performance has succeeded in mediating the relationship with a positive and significant effect. The supporting data dimension for career management has the highest value compared to other dimensions in career management variables and the attitude dimension has the highest value in the competency variable. However, it is also seen that without the mediation of career management, competence has significantly affected performance, this shows that career management mediates competence partially to improve employee performance.

Manajemen karir sebagai mediator The relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance successfully mediates the relationship between organizational commitment and employee performance which relationship if not mediated will not have a significant effect. The supporting data dimension for career management has the highest value compared to other dimensions in career management variables. This shows that career management mediates full organizational commitment, so career management support is needed as a mediator so that organizational commitment can improve employee performance.

B. Recommendation

Based on research that has been done by researchers, this pays attention to the conclusions that have been put forward, then suggestions can be presented that are expected to have benefits and can be used as consideration for further research. From the results of the analysis and conclusions that have

been obtained above, there are several suggestions that might be useful including the following:

➤ *For Organizations*

Based on the competency aspect, the knowledge dimension is the lowest dimension in the competency variable. For this reason, companies need to improve education and training programs in order to improve employee performance.

Based on the aspect of organizational commitment, the dimension of affective commitment is the lowest and needs to be improved. For this reason, the company can hold activities that encourage employees to always be involved in efforts to progress the organization, so that workers have a sense of pride and concern for the company.

Based on the aspect of career management, with the high dimension of supporting data for careers and the low dimension of career opportunities available, the management of PT Nuvision International Indonesia should pay attention to managing organizational career management properly in order to provide opportunities and career paths for employees to realize career success for employees in the company so that it has implications for their performance. Meanwhile, PT Nuvision International Indonesia employees need to improve work competencies to achieve career success such as through non-formal levels by attending training and through formal levels by continuing their studies.

Companies are expected to be able to create work competencies by paying attention to work procedures, preparing employee tasks to be done regularly, fairly, and giving awards to recognize employee achievements and later make employees able to stay in the company. Companies are also expected to provide more career development by paying attention to opportunities for promotion and the need for mentors for informal guidance, so that employees can master the jobs they have in accordance with the responsibilities obtained. In order for employees to last a long time, the company also provides career opportunities for each employee so that career management can run optimally, so that it will improve employee performance in advancing the organization.

➤ *For Researchers*

The results of the study still have a hypothesis that is rejected, namely organizational commitment does not have a significant effect on employee performance, therefore researchers suggest that it can add or expand variables other than those used in this study that affect employee performance such as financial compensation, work ethic, work discipline, and teamwork.

This study only took using 80 samples from workers, it would be better if the samples taken were carried out with a larger sample, so that the results of the study could be generalized in a larger scope, then it was advisable to be able to develop this research by adding objects, respondents, or research variables so as to perfect further research.

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